

RELATIONS BETWEEN CHEMICAL ACTIVITY AND ABSORPTION IN THE
ULTRAVIOLET OF CERTAIN ORGANIC MOLECULES. PART IX.
ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF ISONITROSO DERIVATIVES
OF THE AMIDES OF ACETOACETIC ACID

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The effect of complete transformation of the $-\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}-$ group into $-\text{CO}\cdot\text{C}:\text{NOH}\cdot\text{CO}-$ in the following compounds on absorption in the ultraviolet has been studied: (1) *isonitrosoacetacetanilide*, (2) *isonitrosoacetacet-p-tolylamide*, (3) *isonitrosoacetacet-1:3:4-xylylamide*.

In order to study the changes brought about in light absorption when there is complete transformation of the $-\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}-$ group into $-\text{CO}\cdot\text{C}:\text{NOH}\cdot\text{CO}-$ the following substances have been examined in the ultraviolet.

1. *isoNitrosoacetacetanilide*.
2. *isoNitrosoacetacet-p-tolylamide*.
3. *isoNitrosoacetacet-1:3:4-xylylamide*.

The difference between the structure of the amides and their *isonitroso* derivatives is

It is apparent that in the case of *isonitroso* derivatives there is a total change brought about by the introduction of a double bond in the original $-\text{CO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}-$ complex.

The introduction of a double bond brings about an entirely different energy condition in the molecule. This is translated by increased light absorption and by a totally different disposition of curves of absorption.

In Fig. 1 are traced the curves of absorption spectra of (1) Acetoacetanilide. (2) Acetoacet-*p*-tolylamide. (3) Acetoacet-1:3:4-xylylamide. (4) *isoNitrosoacetacetanilide*. (5) *isoNitrosoacetacet-p-tolylamide*. (6) *isoNitrosoacetacet-1:3:4-xylylamide*.

position of the curves remains always the same. (v) The bases of curves have a tendency to be shifted towards the visible, as also there is a marked sign with regard to a general flattening of the curves.

It is apparent from the curves, that:—(i) The bands have been conspicuously shifted towards the visible. This can be expected from the very colour of the substances as also from the condition of strain established by the double bond in the molecule. (ii) The crests of the curves in the case of the *iso*-nitroso compounds have been practically smoothened out, due to change of structure. (iii) Other characteristics due to the groups which persist unchanged, are still shown by the curves. (iv) The relative position of the curves remains always the same. (v) The bases of curves have a tendency to be shifted towards the visible, as also there is a marked sign with regard to a general flattening of the curves.

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